

NO_x-FREE SOLUTION FOR EMITTER ETCH-BACK

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ABSTRACT: In this paper a novel wet etching solution for emitter etch-back, based on hydrofluoric acid and persulfate, is characterised. The etch rate of this solution is strongly dependent on dopant concentration with an average of 25 nm/min for highly doped emitter surface and below 1 nm/min for lowly doped substrates. The etch rate at a certain dopant concentration is determined by correlation of the removed emitter layer, derived from weight loss, to the emitter profile analysed by secondary ion mass spectroscopy.

Through etch-back the highly doped layer is removed, thus recombination losses at the emitter surface are reduced. The improved emitter quality is confirmed by reduced emitter saturation current density with measured values below 30 fA/cm² and corresponding implied open circuit voltages exceeding 690 mV.

Standard nitric acid based and new etching processes are compared on cell level with NiCu electroplated front contacts as well as with screen printed contacts using a silver paste for lightly doped emitters, both with passivated rear side. On p-type Cz substrates conversion efficiency of 21,0% has been achieved with a homogenous, etched-back emitter and screen printed silver metallisation. For a cell with electroplated NiCu contacts conversion efficiency of 20,9% has been confirmed

Keywords: emitter etch-back, doping profile, saturation current density

1 INTRODUCTION

Emitter etch-back is an applicable processing route to obtain high quality emitter with low dopant surface concentration. An emitter diffused in a standard process and etch-back to e.g. 100 Ω/□ yield lower emitter saturation density than an emitter directly diffused (in a standard single step diffusion) to the same high sheet resistance [1].

Already in 1990 heavy diffusion and emitter etch-back were successfully applied for processing of high efficiency solar cells with evaporated Ti/Pd/Ag front side contacts. The emitter was etched back from e.g. 16 to 80 Ω/□ in a solution containing nitric and hydrofluoric acid [2, 3].

For standard screen printed silver metallisation a relatively high surface dopant concentration, in the order of $5 \cdot 10^{20}$ at/cm³, is required to form low resistivity contacts. Only a slight and precise etch-back of the dead layer and the uppermost highly doped emitter region leads to improved efficiency. Usually alkaline cleaning solutions are applied to remove few nanometers of the emitter surface corresponding to an increase in sheet resistance in the range of 5-10 Ω/□.

In the selective emitter process high dopant concentration underneath the silver paste and low dopant surface concentration between the metallisation fingers are advantageously combined. One processing sequence for selective emitters is single diffusion, masking the metallisation grid and etch-back of unmasked areas. The emitter is etched from e.g. 50 Ω/□ to about 100 Ω/□ [4]. Depending on the emitter profile a layer of 20 to 50 nm has to be removed from the surface. Usually an etching solution of diluted nitric and hydrofluoric acid is used. The etch rate of such a solution is influenced by reaction products; therefore a sophisticated process control is necessary for industrial implementation.

Silicon etching by a mixture of nitric and hydrofluoric acid is described by the following formal reactions.

According to equation 1 the silicon is oxidized by nitric acid. The resulting SiO₂ is then dissolved by hydrofluoric acid (eq. 2). The overall reaction is written in equation 3.

The actual reaction mechanism is much more complex and includes nitrogen intermediate species in the oxidation state +3 such as NO⁺, N₂O₃ and [N₄O₆⁺], comprehensively described in [5]. These N(III) intermediates increase the etch rate of the solution. Freshly prepared HF/HNO₃ solutions or solutions after an idle period need to be activated either by dissolution of silicon or by adding of NaNO₂.

During etching in diluted HF/HNO₃ mixtures porous silicon is formed, which is subsequently removed in an alkaline solution.

The new solution based on hydrofluoric acid and persulfate is stable and easier to control since reaction products do not influence the etch rate. The reaction rate on lowly doped substrates such as typical p-doped silicon with a dopant concentration in the order of 10^{16} at/cm³ is too low to be useful for industrial processes. Therefore this chemistry has not been considered as an option for emitter etching, so far. The presence of dopant atoms in the silicon crystal lattice seems to have a catalytic effect on the etching reaction.

For the HF/persulfate solution following reactions are supposed:

Equation 4 is analogous to equation 3 for HF/nitric acid. Hydrogen evolution as in equation 5 is an alternative reaction route, often described in literature for formation of porous silicon and also for metal assisted etching in HF/H₂O₂ [6].

The etch rate of the HF/persulfate solution is independent of reaction products. No activation is necessary. The etch rate remains stable even after long idle periods. An addition of high amounts of sulfuric or hexafluorosilicic acid to a solution of HF and persulfate do not significantly change the reaction speed, but the formation of porous silicon is avoided. Porous silicon is formed in freshly prepared solutions containing only persulfate and hydrofluoric acid. No visible porous silicon layer is formed in used solutions, in which sulfate, sulfuric acid and hexafluorosilicic acid are present. Apparently the dissolution rate of porous silicon is increased in presence of strong acids.

A similar dependence of the etch rate on dopant concentration is also observed for HF/H₂O₂ containing solutions, but the etch rate is overall lower than in HF/persulfate.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

For etching experiments Boron doped monocrystalline p-type wafers, 2 - 4 Ohmcm were used. The wafers were alkaline textured and cleaned. The emitter diffusion was carried out in a quartz tube furnace with POCl₃ as dopant source.

For cell processing fullsquare, 156 x 156 mm, Boron doped monocrystalline wafers with a base resistivity in the range 1.6 – 1.9 Ohmcm were used. Size 156 mm x Wafer thickness was 200 μm (as cut). After texturing, cleaning and diffusion single side etching in a SCHMID equipment using HF/HNO₃ as etching solution was performed as reference process for edge isolation. Alternatively an experimental single side NO_x-free process was applied. For emitter etch-back a standard laboratory process as a reference and the HF/persulfate solution were used.

Rear side passivation stack as well as the antireflection coating were deposited in a Roth&Rau, MW-PECVD equipment.

Rear side metallisation by screen printing Aluminum paste was carried out after local opening of the passivation layer by laser. For screen printed front side metallisation a silver paste for lightly doped emitters was used.

For electroplated contacts the ARC was opened by laser. Pre-treatment, nickel and copper electroplating were carried out in cup-platers from NB Technologies GmbH. A nickel electrolyte from Schott and a copper electrolyte from Enthone GmbH were used.

Samples for J_{oc} measurement were coated with silicon nitride (as for ARC) on both sides and fired at standard conditions.

3 EMITTER ETCH-BACK

3.1. SIMS Profiles after diffusion

For the experiments two emitter types were used, a standard emitter diffused to 58 Ω/□ and a deep emitter diffused to 25 Ω/□.

Through etch-back from 25 to about 60 Ω/□ the surface dopant concentration is significantly reduced, but the lateral conductivity is still as high as on a standard directly diffused emitter to the same sheet resistance. Therefore a standard front side metallization grid can be

applied [1]. For a high ohmic emitter the spacing between the fingers has to be reduced, leading to higher shadowing losses.

Figure 1: Emitter SIMS profiles directly after diffusion (and glass removal in diluted HF).

3.2. Progressive etch-back

In order to determine the etch rate at a certain dopant concentration wafers with a standard and with a deep emitter were progressively etched back. After each etching step the weight loss and the sheet resistance were determined. The removed emitter thickness was calculated from weight loss and correlated with the dopant concentration from SIMS profiles after diffusion at the calculated depth.

The correlated dopant concentration was then verified by SIMS profiles analyzed on etched-back samples.

Figure 2: Sheet resistance increase on standard and on deep emitter after progressive etching in a solution containing HF and persulfate. Temperature 21 – 22°C.

The weight loss per etching step is very low, about 1 mg, leading to an inaccuracy in the measurements and spreading/inconsistency in calculated etch rate (fig. 3). Nevertheless a clear decrease of the etch rate with progressive etch-back is evident. At the emitter surface the etch rate is approximately 30 nm/min and falls to 3 nm/min at a depth of about 100 nm for the standard emitter. Higher etch rate on the deep emitter at a particular depth is consistent with higher dopant concentration. For comparison the etch rate on textured substrates, without emitter, is on average 0.8 nm/min.

Figure 3: Removed emitter layer calculated from weight loss (upper diagram) and etch rate (lower diagram).

3.3. Etch rate correlation to the dopant concentration.

This correlation is based on calculated removed emitter layer and the corresponding P concentration for the certain depth taken from SIMS profiles after diffusion (fig. 4). The etch rate decreases strongly between $3 \cdot 10^{19}$ and $1 \cdot 10^{19}$ atoms Phosphorus/cm³.

SIMS profiles analyzed on etched-back samples are shown in fig. 5 and fig. 6. Dopant concentrations obtained from weight loss and directly from SIMS profiles on etched samples are compared in Table I.

Table I: Comparison of dopant concentration from SIMS profile after diffusion for removed emitter layer and directly from SIMS profiles on etched-back samples

Removed emitter layer:	[nm]	[at P/cm ³]
Etch-back 58 to 107 Ω/□		
From weight loss	38	$3.5 \cdot 10^{20}$
Directly from profile on etched back sample		$2.0 \cdot 10^{20}$
Etch-back 25 to 57 Ω/□		
From weight loss	105	$1.8 \cdot 10^{20}$
Directly from profile on etched back sample		$2.1 \cdot 10^{20}$
Etch-back 25 to 108 Ω/□		
From weight loss	175	$2.3 \cdot 10^{19}$
Directly from profile on etched back sample		$5.6 \cdot 10^{19}$

On longer etched samples (deep emitter) the correlated P concentration is lower than the actual concentration. The steep decrease of the etching rate might occur already at slightly higher concentration than $3 \cdot 10^{19}$ at P/cm³ as calculated from weight loss.

Figure 4: Etch rate correlated to dopant concentration. Upper diagram: all calculated values, x-axis logarithmic. Lower diagram: P concentration between $1 \cdot 10^{19}$ and $1 \cdot 10^{20}$ at P/cm³, x-axis linear.

3.4 QSSPC measurements

The emitter saturation current density is measured using a standard QSSPC setup with a flash intensity of 45 suns on the wafer and a decay time constant of 2 ms. The evaluation of the emitter saturation current can thus be performed in high injection conditions in the range in between $2 \cdot 10^{16}$ cm⁻³ – $4 \cdot 10^{16}$ cm⁻³. Measurements are performed on 5 positions on the wafer, in the centre and in the 4 edges. The average of these 5 values is displayed in table II.

Table II: Emitter saturation current density and implied open circuit voltage

Emitter	J_{0e} [fA/cm ²]	Impl. Voc [mV]
Directly after diffusion to 58 Ω/□	251	650
Etched back from 58 to 96 Ω/□	58	685
Etched back from 25 to 60 Ω/□	114	669
Etched back from 25 to 99 Ω/□	28	693

Very good J_{0e} values down to 30 fA/cm² and implied V_{oc} values up to 690 mV are measured on the etched back samples. These very good results on wafer basis are confirmed in section 4 by cell results with open circuit voltage exceeding 660 mV. Very similar results were obtained for all etched-back emitter types. Contrary to expectation based on J_{0e} values the best efficiency was measured for the standard emitter, i.e. etched-back from about 60 Ω/□ to about 100 Ω/□.

Figure 5: SIMS profiles after diffusion and on etched-back samples. Standard emitter.

3.5. Etching homogeneity

No difference in etching homogeneity between the reference laboratory process and the HF/persulfate (HF/PS) solution was observed. In table III examples on two different material types, both after standard diffusion to 60 Ω/\square are given. In fig. 7 a sheet resistance map is depicted. The map shows the same distribution as usually observed directly after POCl_3 -diffusion, which confirms the etching uniformity.

Table III: Comparison of etching homogeneity by sheet resistance measurement

Wafer	Solution	Mean [Ω/\square]	Std. dev. [Ω/\square]	Min [Ω/\square]	Max [Ω/\square]
Type 1	Reference	92.1	3.0	86	98
Type 2	Reference	96.0	4.7	88	105
Type 1	HF/PS	86.0	2.7	83	92
Type 2	HF/PS	90.3	3.6	84	98

Figure 7: Sheet resistance map, measured on AR coating. Mean: 112,0 Ω/\square , std. dev. 5,8, minimum 99,5, maximum 124,8 Ω/\square .

4 CELL RESULTS

4.1. Cells with screen printed front metallization

The process sequence is rather simple: alkaline texturing, cleaning, POCl_3 diffusion. The wet processes are described in detail in fig. 8. Beside the NO_x -free emitter etch also an experimental NO_x -free edge isolation was used. Subsequently passivation processes are

Figure 6: SIMS profiles after diffusion and on etched-back samples. Deep emitter.

applied, the rear side is opened by laser, followed by screen printing front and rear and firing.

Standard Etching Sequence	NO_x -free Process
Edge Isolation HF/ HNO_3 (silicon removal 1.8-2.3 μm)	Emitter Etch-Back HF/Persulfate
PSG Removal HF	
Standard Emitter Etch-Back	NO_x -free Edge Isolation (silicon removal 1.5-1.8 μm)
Cleaning	Cleaning

Figure 8: Etching sequence for screen-printed cells with standard and with NO_x -free processes

Cell results confirm the equal performance of both processing routes (table IV).

Table IV: Cell results with screen printed metallization; standard front side layout. Average of 8 cells. (Sheet resistance measured on ARC.)

Emitter	Voc	Jsc	FF	η
Etch-back 60 to 112 Ω/\square	mV	mA/cm^2	%	%
Standard process	662	39.5	78.9	20.6
NO_x -free process	661	39.6	78.9	20.6

With etched-back emitter and improved front side layout cells with 21,0% efficiency have been achieved, independently confirmed by ISE CalLab. The cell parameters are displayed in Table V.

Table V: Best screen printed cell with optimized front side layout

Emitter	Voc	Jsc	FF	η
Etch-back 60 to 112 Ω/\square	mV	mA/cm^2	%	%
	664	39.9	79.2	21.0

4.2. Cells with direct electroplated Nickel – Copper contacts.

After screen printing Al paste and firing the ARC was opened by laser. The laser parameters were adjusted for a complete ablation of the AR coating, preferably without any damage to the emitter. However the removal

of few nanometers of the emitter was inevitable, resulting in increased sheet resistance on ablated areas. Thus the dopant concentration underneath the electroplated contacts is even lower than measured on etched-back wafers.

For NiCu contacts usually a thermal treatment for silicide formation is carried out after plating. In our experiment the series resistance and the fill factor were not improved after a silicidation step at 250°C (in air atmosphere). The cell parameters remained unchanged even after two silicidation steps for 5 minutes. Also the adhesion was only slightly improved through the thermal treatment as described above. The measured peel strength was 1.3 N (per 1 mm bus bar width; 180° peel angle) without thermal treatment and 1.5 N after silicidation. Therefore all cells described in table VI and VII were not thermally treated after plating.

Since the cells were processed only for experimental purposes no protective layer was applied on top of the NiCu stack as it is necessary to avoid copper oxidation.

Table VI: Cell results with NiCu contacts and standard front side layout (all cells with NO_x-free processes; sheet resistance measured on ARC.)

Emitter	V _{oc} mV	J _{sc} mA/cm ²	FF %	η %
No etch-back 65 Ω/□	649	39.3	79.6	20.3
Etch-back 60 to 120 Ω/□	661	39.8	79.0	20.8
Etch-back 25 to 65 Ω/□	659	39.6	79.3	20.7
Etch-back 25 to 120 Ω/□	660	39.5	79.3	20.7

Using the described processing sequence best results were obtained with standard emitter and etch-back to about 120 Ω/□. The open circuit voltage and short circuit current density were significantly improved, resulting in 0,5%(abs.) efficiency gain. For the deep emitter slightly lower J_{sc} values were observed.

With improved front side layout cells with higher efficiency have been achieved. The cell parameters of a cell independently measured by ISE CalLab are displayed in Table VII.

Table VII: Cell with NiCu contacts and improved front side layout

Emitter	V _{oc} mV	J _{sc} mA/cm ²	FF %	η %
Etch-back 60 to 120 Ω/□	663	39.8	79.3	20.9

5 SUMMARY

Emitter etching in a solution containing hydrofluoric acid and persulfate is possible without additional catalyst. For the applied etching composition and at ambient temperature the etch rate is about 25 nm/min on the highly doped emitter surface. This is not very fast, but well suited for removing a layer of 20 to 50 nm as required for etch-back of standard emitters.

The etch rate decreases at a dopant concentration of approx. 3 · 10¹⁹ atoms/cm³ by one order of magnitude.

Contrary to HF/HNO₃ the etch rate of a solution of HF and persulfate is independent of reaction products providing stable processing conditions. During etching no NO_x-gases are evolved.

Remarkable efficiency enhancements make the homogenous etched-back emitter interesting for industrial use. State-of-the-art silver pastes are capable for contacting emitters with approximately 2 · 10²⁰ atoms Phosphorus/cm³. This is a huge progress in screen printed metallisation. Further efficiency improvements through layout optimisation, thinner fingers and stencil printing are conceivable. At the same time the deposited silver paste amount is reduced, which means cost savings.

Direct Nickel / Copper plating offers much lower metal costs and the ability to contact emitters with even lower dopant concentration. However, in our experiment no further improvement by strong etching-back from 25 to 120 Ω/□ was observed compared to etch-back from 60 to about 120 Ω/□, in spite of very low emitter saturation current density. This might be attributed to the applied processing.

The ability to use silver paste on lightly doped emitters in connection with decreasing paste deposit mitigates the technological and cost pressure to replace this established technology by electroplating.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] B. Raabe, F. Book, A. Dastgheib-Shirazi, G. Hahn, "The Development of Etch-Back Processes for Industrial Silicon Solar Cells", *Proceedings of the 25th EU PVSEC*, Valencia, 2010
- [2] Narayanan, S. Wenham, M. Green, "17.8-Percent Efficiency Polycrystalline Silicon Solar Cells", *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 382-384, 1990
- [3] P. Sana, J. Salami, A. Rohatgi, "Fabrication and Analysis of High-Efficiency Polycrystalline Solar Cells", *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 40, no. 8, pp. 1461-1467, 1993
- [4] A. Dastgheib-Shirazi, H. Haverkamp, B. Raabe, F. Book, G. Hahn, "Selective Emitter for Industrial Solar Cell Production: a Wet Chemical Approach Using a Single Diffusion Process", *Proceedings of the 23rd EU PVSEC*, Valencia, 2008
- [5] M. Steinert, J. Acker, M. Krause, S. Oswald, K. Wetzig, "Reactive Species Generated during Wet Chemical Etching of Silicon in HF/HNO₃ mixtures", *J. Phys. Chem. B*, vol. 110, pp. 11377-11382, 2006
- [6] Bastide, C. Chartier, C. Vard, C. Lèvy-Clément, "Multicrystalline Si Texturization by Metal-Assisted Chemical Etching for Solar Cell Applications", *Proceedings of the 22nd EU PVSEC*, Milano, 2007